

A Finite element representation of Time

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to consider the possibility of understanding gravity through the use of information. In this case, information is stored in space-time as finite elements. Thus, in the introduction to the paper, a general aspect of gravity, which is gravitational redshift and blueshift is considered through the use of finite elements. The result is that gravity is considered to be best described as a field of P-refined elements with a null space. Next, it is shown that this definition of gravity through the use of information stored in such elements could be combined with a deterministic interpretation of quantum mechanics (Bohmian mechanics), although at a very superficial level. Next, an attempt is made to apply this technique to black holes, particularly utilizing the Ted Jacobson approach where the Einstein field equations is developed as an Equation of state. The result obtained is that a direct association is implied between entropy as defined in the text and the rate at which time flows on every level in the universe. This relationship is then used in an extremely simple thought experiment to simulate relativity in time based on the conservation of entropy principles defined using time reversal symmetry as it is applied to classical electromagnetic fields. Finally, the case is made that based on the associated definitions of time developed, information will never be lost in a black-hole even in cases where the horizon area reduces. The appendix section aims to show how Hawking's temperature and mass relationship for black holes can also be reproduced using some of the definitions made in the text.

Keywords: Bohmian mechanics, Information, Entropy

1. Introduction

A Finite element is a great tool for describing the laws of physics, particularly or especially those based on space and time dependent parameters. This is usually because most space and time based phenomena are expressed using partial differential equations, some of which for example non-linear ones have no exact analytical solutions. Therefore, finite elements intuitively seem to offer some real insight into space and time beyond what equations sometimes on their own might be able to, therefore the aim of this paper is to see if some general ideas of gravity can be modelled or represented using Finite elements.

1.1 Gravity

A starting point for understanding gravity through finite elements might be seen when one considers the notion of gravitational red-shift. For example, suppose one has 10 finite elements representing a certain frequency of light. If it is assumed that each point in space-time is represented or can be fully represented using finite elements, then the question arises that if one is to maintain accuracy in this representation of space-time using finite elements, then how many elements should be used for representing red light VS blue light? This question is important because it might open an avenue for understanding how information can be represented in such a scenario. Of course, it has been rightly

predicted in the General theory of relativity that light redshifts away from a gravitational source and blue-shifts towards the source of gravity. In his essay on how many Elements per wavelengths are necessary, Steffen Marburg rightly explains that in order to maintain the desired accuracy, a fixed number of elements per wavelengths are necessary. (Marburg S, 2018). The general rule therefore is that for accuracy to be maintained, which has to be held should one chose to represent space-time using finite elements, this is necessary because the laws of physics have to be the same no matter how many elements one choses, so the speed of light cannot change in any region of space-time, then one will need more elements per wavelength.

So what does that mean? Well if each region of space-time is attributed an equal number of finite elements, because one treats space-time as a homogeneous medium, then in order to maintain an equal amount of accuracy, then how does one treat regions where light is blue-shifted for example, regions towards a gravitational field which requires less elements?

Suppose each region of space-time one is working in at each scale contains 10 elements, then there would be no problem representing light of the highest wavelength. One simply has to correspond the highest number of elements for each region to the highest wavelength, such that the highest number of elements in each region of space-time is enough to represent accurately the highest wavelength of light. However, because each region of space-time contains the highest number of elements, representing lower wavelengths with this same number of elements would increase the accuracy in that region of space-time. In such a case then, the laws of physics would be different and one might have light going at different speeds. However, from experience, one knows that this is not true, therefore, one needs to introduce a finite element concept known as P-refinement to solve this dilemma,

The P refinement refers to changing the degree of the highest complete polynomial within an element. In the case presented for blue light which has a shorter wavelength, without removing elements from each specific region where blue light is present, one can simply P-refine, some of the elements in that region of space-time and assume that the remaining elements in that region represent the null space of the P-refined elements, By remaining elements, what is meant is that one will keep the number of elements in all regions of space-time constant, but instead of using all the elements, one can P-refine the order(degree of freedom) of some of the elements while making some of the unused elements the null space of those elements. Hence, one can maintain the accuracy in that space while using fewer elements.

The question then arise, instead of P refining (that is increasing the degree of freedom of a few elements), or rather letting a few elements contain all the information about the blue light, why not use 8 of the 10 elements in that space-time region and let all the other 2 elements be their null space. The answer would be that space-time is relative and hence the information contained in the 8 elements as pertains blue light is greater than that contained in the 2 elements. Thus, from the perspective of the 2 elements, the 8 elements have been P refined, that is they can contain more information than the 2 elements. Therefore, using finite elements to represent any region of space-time, gravity is analogous to a P-refined field of elements that contains a null space of extra elements. Another way of saying this is that any region of space-time where one uses only some of the elements to represent all the information, with the remaining elements posing as a null space is a gravitational field. This connection is based on the fact that each region of space-time maintains the same accuracy. The image below depicts a P-refined elements VS a normal unrefined element. Please note that in this version of space-time, increasing the maximum number of elements in a particular region of space-time would be impossible. This is done so as to represent space-time as a homogenous medium.

Figure 1 Normal Element vs P refined element

Element A is a typical element in each region of space-time while element B is a P refined element which represents an element in a gravitational field. Notice that element A has 4 nodes while element B has 8 nodes, Supposing each element has 1 degree of freedom, then from the perspective of element A, element B has 8 degrees of freedom or 4 degrees of freedom higher than element A. Also from the perspective of A, element B will be a curved space, because there are extra degrees of freedom in a curved space(for example the sum of angles in a triangle is not 180° in curved space due owing to the extra degrees of freedom.)

Thus, if each region of space-time is represented using an equal number of finite elements, in order to maintain

accuracy, redlight will need a higher number of elements than bluelight, and this can be achieved by the use of P-refinements and a null space, The question then arises, in a gravitational field represented by a few P refined elements, what does the null space(the other elements in that region of space-time that are not P refined) represent?

Intuitively speaking, a null space can be represented as any set of information that when added to a particular system leaves the system changeless. For example, suppose one represents a system with matrix A as the range of all possible rates of return that are achievable. The null space of matrix A are the investmensts that can be made that will not change the rates of return on the investments. Another system that can be represented with the same matrix A could be the density and flux of energy and momentum in spacetime. Thus, the null space of such a matrix would be any set of information (possibly any additional amount of energy and momentum that when added leaves this) physical system changeless. Supposing the same Matrix represents the wavefunction(or rather quantum state of an isolated quantum system), then its null space would represent how much one does not know about the quantum state of an isolated system. In the representation of space-time using finite elements, elements that are P refined represent gravitational fields (hence they contain information about the density and flux of energy and momentum of a particular system). However, the P-refined elements also represent the state of an isolated quantum system. Thus, if one combines both concepts, then the wavefunction represented by the P-refined elements would represent information about the state of energy and momentum of an isolated quantum system. Assuming in the case of the gravitational field, the exact amount of energy and momentum would be known, therefore one also assumes that the exact amount of energy and momentum of the quantum system are known. Thus, using the uncertainty principle, it is safe to say that one does not know the position of the particles that represent the quantum sysetem, that is one does not know the state of the position of the particles that are represented by the quantum system. Thus, the absolute position of the particles would be in the null space (represented by the unused elements in that region of space-time). The absolute position of a particle in space-time does not provide any extra information about its gravitational field, thus it seems reasonable to define the null space as containng this information. Therefore, it is implied that the ignorance in the position of particles leads to the randomness of quantum mechanics and this is shown below.

1.1.1 Proof.

In Bohmian mechanics, the complete state of the whole system of particles in the universe, say N, is given by the universal wavefunction $\Psi(x, t)$ with $x = \{x_1, x_2... x_N\}$, and by

the actual positions of the particles $X(t) = \{X_1(t), X_2(t)... X_N(t)\}$. The universal wavefunction evolves according to the many particle Schrodinger equation:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial t} = \hat{H} \Psi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \left(\sum_{j=1}^N -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_j} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_j^2} + U(\mathbf{x}, t) \right) \Psi(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad (1)$$

where m_i is the mass of the i -th particle and the Hamiltonian operator \hat{H} contains, both, the kinetic energy term and the potential energy term, $U(x, t)$, of all the particles.

The following continuity equation for the modulus squared of the wavefunction can be obtained from the above equation (1) as:

$$\frac{\partial |\Psi(\mathbf{x}, t)|^2}{\partial t} + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (|\Psi(\mathbf{x}, t)|^2 v_i(\mathbf{x}, t)) = 0. \quad (2)$$

Now suppose that one does not know the initial positions of the particles, but that one assumes that they are in accordance with a given statistical distribution $p(x,0)$. It follows from equation 2 that if this initial distribution is given by $p(x,0) = |\Psi(x, 0)|^2$; then the dynamics preserves this form of the distribution: that is for any future time t , the distribution is $p(x,t) = |\Psi(x, t)|^2$. When the distribution is preserved by the dynamics, as happens for $p(x,0) = |\Psi(x, 0)|^2$, one can say that the distribution is equivariant.

Hence, any evolution of a system(subsystem or the entire universe) is determined by when both the initial positions of its constituent particles and its effective wavefunction are preseved. (Solé et al., 2016). However, since one does not have complete knowledge about the initial position of particles, their evolution will appear random.

2. Black Hole Thermodynamics

Using the same principles as stated previously, one can apply the use of finite elements to black holes. But before doing so, one can try to come up with an understanding of what time represents using finite element. By representing each field or rather region of space-time using finite elements, space-time can easily be understood as a region containing a number of elements The curvature of that space-time is understood or has been shown to be the amount of P refinement in that region(that is the no of elements that have been P refined), but in order to combine space and time using finite elements, a problem that arises naturally becomes what is time in this representation? It has been shown using general relativity that time slows down due to the presence of a gravitational field (Austin, 2017) and this is generally referred to as time dilation. It has also been explained here

that P refined elements contains more information relative to other elements in a region of space-time. In his paper on the Gibbs paradox and the concepts of information, similarity, and their relationship, Shu-Kin-Lin proposes three laws of entropy and in the third law, he states that structures are symmetric at maximum entropy, hence one can infer from this that assymetric structures have zero or minimum entropy (Lin, 2008). Thus, in a P refined region containing a minimum entropy such as a gravitational field, time runs slower, and one can represent time as the amount of symmetry of the elements used to construct that region of space. For gravitational fields, where time runs slower, due to containing a high amount of information, one can deduce that the elements(finite elements) are assymetic, while for the null space represented using the remaniing elements in that region, one can describe as symmetric. Therefore, the rate at which time flows in any region is determined by the symmetry of the finite elements in that region, which is based on the entropy(lack of information) in that region. This, time moves slower in a region of P-refinement and the greater the P-refinement, the greater the time dilation.

Suppose each region of space-time of equal dimensions (equal light distances) can be represented using 10 elements. Gravitational fields for example, those of the sun or the moon might be represented with 9 of the 10 elements, while those of black holes would need to be represented using fewer elements due to higher P refinements. Thus a black hole might be represented using 1 or 2 P refined elements. For black holes, it is known that they contain singularities and these points are inaccessible for outside observers, therefore, suppose one assumes that in a region of space-time represented with 10 elements, just as every other region, a black hole exists. If one represents the gravitational field of the black hole using 3 P refined elements, then there will be 7 elements in that region constituting its null space. From current understanding, it is knownt that those 3 elements will be inaccessible, due to the nature of singularities in black holes, hence what would happen if any matter falls into the black hole? Any increase in the mass of the black hole would increase the amount of P refinement in that region (hence there would be a decrease in the number of elements used to represent the gravitational field. In this case, if 3 P-refined elements were previously used to represent the gravitational field, as the black hole increases in mass, there would come a time where instead of 3 elements, it would be 2 elements that would be used to represent the gravitational field, Consequently, there will also be an increase in the number of elements that constitute its null space (8 rather than 7). In such a scenario, the entropy of the null space constituting the remaining elements in this case 8 of them would increase (this is because entropy can be defined as the multipicity of the stores of information or the multiplicity of the finite elements).

In black hole thermodynamics, the entropy (S_{BH}) of a black hole is given by the formula below (Hawking, 1976):

$$\frac{K A}{4 l^2} \quad (3)$$

Where l^2 is the $l_{planck}^2 = \frac{hG}{c^3} = (10^{-33} \text{ cm})^2$, K is the Boltzmann's constant

In this case, the surface area of the black hole horizon area would be related to the number of elements representing the null space by:

$$A = \ln(\text{no of elements}) \quad (4)$$

In his paper on the Thermodynamics of space-time: The Einstein equation of state, Ted Jacobson shows how the relationship between entropy and horizon area together with the fundamental relation $dQ = Tds$ connecting heat, entropy and temperature can be used to derive the Einstein equation (Jacobson, 1995). Using these in addition to the above definition of the horizon area, the nature of the cosmological constant is defined as:

Cosmological constant = total no of elements in universe

It can be gotten from:

$\ln(\text{no of elements in singularity}) + \ln(\text{no of elements in observable universe or space-time})$. Thus, if the no of elements in singularity increase, then the number of elements in the universe will decrease.

2.1 Proof

$$R_{ab} - \frac{1}{2} R_{gab} + \Lambda_{gab} = \frac{2\pi}{h\eta} T_{ab} \quad (5)$$

$$4hG = 1/\eta, \eta = 1/4hG \quad (6)$$

$$R_{ab} - \frac{1}{2} R_{gab} + \Lambda_{gab} = 8\pi G T_{ab} \quad (7)$$

$$\eta = \frac{1}{4hG} \quad (8)$$

$$Tds = \left(\frac{hk}{2\pi}\right) \frac{1}{4hG} dA \quad (9)$$

$$Tds = \frac{k}{8\pi G} dA \quad (10)$$

$$8\pi G = kdA \quad (11)$$

$$8\pi G = \frac{kdA}{Tds}, ds = \frac{dQ}{T} \quad (12)$$

$$8\pi G = \frac{kdA}{dQ} \quad (13)$$

$$R_{ab} - \frac{1}{2} R_{gab} + \Lambda_{gab} = 8\pi G T_{ab} \quad (14)$$

$$R_{ab} - \frac{1}{2} R_{gab} + \Lambda_{gab} = \frac{kdA}{dQ} T_{ab} \quad (15)$$

$$\delta Q = \int_{\mathcal{H}} T_{ab} \chi^a d\Sigma^b,$$

$$\delta Q = -\kappa \int_{\mathcal{H}} \lambda T_{ab} k^a k^b d\lambda dA. \quad (16)$$

$$\text{Assuming } dQ = T_{ab}K \quad (17)$$

Where $K = \text{nat}$ (natural unit of information) (18)

$$R_{ab} - \frac{1}{2} R_{gab} + \Lambda_{gab} = dA \quad (19)$$

$$A = \ln(\text{no of elements in null space}) \quad (20)$$

This derivation occurs for 0 cosmological constant. Note, cosmological constant is defined as:

$\ln(\text{no of elements in singularity}) + \ln(\text{no of elements in space-time})$. For cosmological constant to be 0, it is shown that:

$$0 = \ln(\text{no of elements in singularity}) + \ln\left\{\frac{1}{(\text{no of elements in singularity})}\right\} \quad (21)$$

$$\text{Therefore, } \ln(\text{no of elements in } A) = \ln(1/(\text{no of elements in singularity})) \quad (22)$$

Thus, in limit of 0 cosmological constant:

$$R_{ab} - \frac{1}{2} R_{gab} + \Lambda_{gab} = dA$$

$$\text{Where no of elements in horizon area} = \frac{1}{\text{no of elements in singularity}} \quad (23)$$

Alternatively, $A = \ln(\text{no of elements in horizon area})$

$$\text{Thus } dA = \frac{1}{\text{no of elements in horizon area}} \quad (24)$$

In the limit of 0 cosmological constant or infinite mass black hole,

$$R_{ab} - \frac{1}{2} R_{gab} + \Lambda_{gab} = \frac{1}{\text{no of elements in horizon area}} \quad (25)$$

Area (Horizon area) = $\ln(\text{no of elements})$

$$\text{Curvature} = \frac{1}{\text{no of elements in horizon area}} \quad (26)$$

Thus, Area (horizon area) = $\ln(1/\text{curvature})$ (27)

Assume curvature = x , (28)

Area (horizon area) = $\ln(1/x)$ (29)

$$\frac{dAREA}{dx} = \frac{-1}{x} \quad (30) \text{ where } x = \text{curvature, AREA} = \text{HORIZON AREA}$$

$$S_{BH} = \frac{1}{4} \frac{A}{l^2} \quad (31)$$

Where A is the horizon area

As is shown above, the change in the horizon area is ≤ 0 , therefore the change in entropy of a black hole should always be negative or 0, and hence a black hole always almost decreases in entropy. Thus entropy should always increase in the observable universe. The relation between this phenomenon and P-refinement will be explained more clearly in the rest of the text. As can be seen in the derivation, the total number of elements in the universe is reducing, thus the level of P-refinement is reducing as well. This is because the number of possible arrangements or stores of information (finite elements) in space-time has reduced, hence the level of P-refinement as well. Note that in any region of space-time represented using finite elements, the greater the amount of P-refinement, the greater the amount of elements in the null space, consequently if there are less elements in the null space, then the P refinement in that region is lower. Thus, the reduction in the total number of elements in the universe means that at any local level, the level of P refinement is lower hence the level of asymmetry in that region is lower. Thus time will run faster across each region of the universe in such a case. Therefore, one consequence of this is that time runs faster than any previous instant on each local level, because P refinement is reducing.

Another way of looking at this is by considering the fact that because there are less possible stores of information (finite elements) and hence the symmetry in each region has increased. Hence any clock at any position in space-time represented using finite elements will tick faster at moment 2 than at moment 1 and at moment 3 than moment 2 and so on. Note however that gravity is not reducing locally because there is no change in the null space of each region locally

(that is in any region far away from the singularity, the no of elements is not reducing).

2.2 Time increase

John W. Norbury correctly stated in his paper on “the invariance of classical electromagnetism under charge conjugation, parity and time reversed (CPT) transformations that a charged particle in an electric and magnetic field has reflection and time reversal symmetry. Thus, entropy in such a system is conserved, according to Noether’s theorem (Norbury, 1990)

It has been assumed that as entropy increases in space-time modelled using finite elements, time runs faster. Thus for any event in such a space-time, on a local level, time will run faster at moment 1 than moment 0, and at moment 2 than moment 1 and so on. However, any region in space-time that represents classical electromagnetism must represent a conservation of entropy. This is because an electromagnetic field must be invariant under reflection and time symmetry.

Assuming a train is travelling at 0.95c where c is the speed of light and a man is on the rail track. In space-time modelled using finite elements, time runs faster at every moment, because of an increase in entropy. So assuming that the increase in time in each subsequent moment for a passenger on the train and the man in the rail track is the same, then they would not be able to say that time flows faster for one or the other. Time will flow at the same rate for each of them. However, suppose that the speed of an electromagnetic field conserves entropy, as shown below:

Figure 2 Motion of a positive charge moving towards a mirror with an initial velocity V in a uniform electric field. The position of the charge at various times is indicated with the positive + symbol, at time t equal time intervals are indicated (Norbury J, 1990).

Figure 3 Motion of figure 2 in reflected mirror (Norbury J, 1990).

Thus, as the passenger in the train approaches c, his rate of change of entropy approaches 0 (because c conserves entropy). Furthermore, because time gets faster in each successive moment as entropy increases, time for the man on the rail track will only get faster (because he is not moving at a high speed, only standing still). Thus, if the man in the train moving at a high speed (0.95c), looks at the clock of the man on the rail track, time will seem to be faster (precisely because entropy is far from being conserved in his region), and if the man on the rail track looks at the clock on the man in the train moving at 0.95c, it would appear to be moving very slowly (because entropy is almost conserved) in his region. If entropy is a macroscopic quantity, then this relativity in time as observed due to conservation of entropy will only apply to macroscopic systems.

Another plausible explanation can be seen based on the fact that in space-time modelled using finite elements, time runs faster in each subsequent moment due to an increase in entropy (the total number of elements in the universe decreases, thus the level of P refinement decreases), thus $dt > 0$ and time seems to run faster when entropy is conserved ($dt = 0$), hence it has been shown that in black holes entropy decreases, due to the fact that $dA \leq 0$; however a decrease in entropy would mean that $dt < 0$; thus using the second law of thermodynamics proposed by Hawking for black holes:

$$\frac{dA}{dt}$$

It can be seen that

$$\frac{dA}{dt} \geq 0; \text{ where } dA \leq 0 \text{ and } dt \leq 0$$

Thus even though black holes area reduces, this is compensated for by the fact that time moves slower in each subsequent moment than in each previous moment ($dt < 0$); hence information is never destroyed in black holes.

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Appendix

Assuming temperature increases as the degree of freedom increases. Then, temperature can be represented in a black hole as a P-refinement. Thus, $T = \ln(\text{no of elements in singularity})$. Using Hawking's equation, temperature varies inversely with the mass of a black hole. Assuming for the sake of simplicity, that the curvature of space-time increases linearly with mass, we can also define mass as X (same as curvature), thus one gets:

$$\frac{dT}{dx} = \frac{1}{x}$$

For the derivation obtained previously

$$\frac{dA}{dx} = \frac{-1}{x}$$

Where x is curvature

Thus $dT = -dA$

Therefore, $T = -\ln(\text{no of elements in horizon area})$

No of elements in singularity = 1/no of elements in Horizon area

Based on the definition of the cosmological constant

$$dt = -dA$$

Thus the formula $\frac{dT}{dx} = \frac{1}{x}$ can be easily derived from the above definition of the cosmological constant and $\frac{dA}{dx} = \frac{-1}{x}$

This is because in space-time modelled using finite elements, an increase in P refinement as explained previously is an increase in the degree of freedom of elements used to P refine. This is analogous to temperature. Also important is the fact that as temperature increases, the wavelength emitted gets shorter, which requires fewer elements, which is analogous to a (P refinement)